

**PREMIERE –
PREPARING MULTI-
ACTOR PROJECTS
IN A CO-CREATIVE WAY**

GA No. 101086531

**FINAL REPORT of PREMIERE Focus Group #3:
'OG go Horizon'**

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**Role and importance of EIP-AGRI
Operational Group members in
Horizon Europe Multi-Actor projects**

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REPORT of PREMIERE Focus Group #3:
'OG go Horizon'– Role and importance of EIP-AGRI
Operational Groups in Horizon Europe Multi-Actor
projects

MAIN AUTHORS

Albert Escolà (DARPA)
Lluc Tost (DARPA)
Hanna Tamsalu (METK)
Susanne v. Münchhausen (HNEE)

WITH CONTRIBUTIONS FROM

Participants of the Focus Group
Jordi Pietx (HCC)
All partner teams

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ACRONYMS

Acronym	Long Form
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy of the EU
DG AGRI	Directorate-General of the European Commission for Agriculture and Rural Development
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability
EU	European Union
FG	Focus Group
HEU	<p>Horizon Europe, the European Union's research and innovation framework programme (2021–2027).</p> <p>In the context of Horizon Europe clusters" refer to major thematic areas: Cluster 6: "Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment".</p> <p>The Soil Mission is one of five EU Missions established under Horizon Europe, it has its own dedicated Work Programme.</p>
MA, MAA	<p>Multi-Actor, Multi-Actor Approach</p> <p>The specific version of the MAA is defined by DG AGRI for Cluster 6 and Horizon Soil Mission projects.</p>
NCP	National Contact Points are people nominated by the national authorities in Member States and Associated Countries to provide assistance to potential Horizon Europe applicants in their countries.
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OG	<p>EIP-AGRI Operational Group at the member state (MS) level. An Operational Group may include various actors from AKIS, including farmers, foresters, researchers, advisors, businesses, environmental groups, consumer interest groups or other NGOs to advance innovation for agriculture, forestry and rural areas.</p> <p>https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/operational-groups_en</p>
PREMIERE	PREMIERE is a European Union funded project that aims to strengthen the multi-actor approach by supporting the development of more relevant, coherent, and well-prepared project proposals.
R&I	Research and Innovation project in the Horizon Europe context
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

Table 1: List of acronyms

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Focus Group 3 of the PREMIERE project addressed the **specific role and importance of EIP-AGRI Operational Group (OG) members in Horizon Europe Multi-Actor projects.**

The European Commission expects many more interactive innovation groups (incl Operational Groups) from the grassroots level to be included in Horizon cluster 6 and Soil Mission proposals. As the European Commission increases the number of call topics requiring the MAA within Cluster 6 and Soil Mission, it is essential to establish an enabling environment where grassroots innovation groups can contribute effectively to European research and innovation. This report evaluates the current landscape of these collaborations, identifying the challenges faced by both practitioners experienced in interactive innovation projects and project coordinators while offering a roadmap for improved integration in future work programmes.

The findings presented here are derived from a co-creative process that began with an online survey in March 2025, which collected 124 responses from a balanced mix of OG members and Horizon Europe experts. These insights provided the foundation for an online workshop held on April 7, 2025, where 23 participants from diverse geographic regions and stakeholder categories engaged in breakout sessions to discuss inclusion, funding, and the functional roles of practitioners. This comprehensive approach ensured that the recommendations are grounded in the real-world experiences of those navigating the intersection of national CAP and European research funding connected by the rationale of the policy framework of the European Innovation Partnership (EIP-AGRI).

A central finding of this Focus Group is that current Horizon Europe guidelines do not sufficiently clarify why OGs should be engaged or how they are expected to contribute to specific project outcomes. This lack of clarity is compounded by administrative and financial barriers, which practitioners identified as their primary challenges. Legal and administrative uncertainty remains a deterrent, particularly for OGs that are not established as formal legal entities and struggle to sign official documents like non-disclosure agreements.

The report further identifies a significant conceptual barrier that limits meaningful participation. The specific language in Horizon Europe documentation often excludes farmers and local business owners who possess vital tacit knowledge but lack specialized staff or advice for complex administration. Furthermore, timing of OG and HEU projects of the same or similar topic are not aligned – projects never run in parallel for a long time.

To bridge these gaps, the Focus Group recommends that evaluators rigorously assess the application of the Multi-Actor Approach, rejecting proposals that treat (OG) practitioners as "token" participants rather than core contributors. **Policy documents should provide clear, practical examples of flexible involvement, such as allowing individual motivated members to represent an OG** rather than requiring the entire consortium to join, which reduces legal and administrative complexity.

Improved coordination between National Contact Points and CAP Networks is also vital to ensure that practitioners receive the tailored support and "seed" funding necessary to build trust-based relationships with European research networks.

The Commission's understanding is based on the assumption that the integration of OGs into Horizon Europe holds the potential to accelerate the development of innovative solutions that are grounded in real-world needs. By addressing systemic informational and administrative obstacles, the European Union aims to unlock the full potential of innovation, fostering a more resilient and competitive agri-food sector that effectively addresses evolving societal and environmental challenges.

1 CONTEXT

This Focus Group 3 of the PREMIERE project addressed the specific role and importance of **EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (OGs)** in Horizon Europe Multi-Actor (MA) projects.

OGs under the European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI) play a pivotal role in fostering innovation within the agricultural and rural sectors of the European Union. By bringing together farmers, researchers, advisors, and businesses, OGs serve as a collaborative platform for developing practical and innovative solutions to agricultural challenges. According to its representatives, the European Commission expects many more interactive innovation groups (incl OGs) from the grass-root level to be included in Horizon proposals.

The Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) in Horizon Europe ensures that all representatives of all relevant stakeholder groups for the project's objectives are involved from the outset. It fosters co-creation among actors with complementary knowledge from science and practice to collaboratively implement the work plan of the research and innovation (R&I) project.

The working question for the Focus Group discussion was: “How to involve 'Operational Groups' in EU-funded multi-actor projects as required by several Calls of the Horizon Research and Innovation programme?”

Experience from practice show that many OG projects are led by professional organisations such as chambers of agriculture, public advisory services, universities or applied research institutes. These organisations often also engage in EU R&I programmes. However, smaller or more locally embedded OG members have been often disconnected from HEU programmes so far. This Focus Group aimed to study the particular challenges and opportunities for newcomer OG members when willing to engage in HEU project applications.

The Focus Group aimed to engage with relevant key actors and key stakeholders to reach the following objectives:

- Evaluate the current situation of OGs in MA European projects.
- Identify main challenges of OG members or representatives in HEU.
- Describe possibilities to achieve an increase in the participation of OG members in HEU.

2 DESIGN OF THE FOCUS GROUP

To reach the objectives, several steps were planned for the Focus Group process:

- Survey in March 2025 to gather insights, and to learn from people that are currently working or have worked with OGs, what are the barriers, and setbacks that they have; also to learn what are their benefits and what opportunities do they see. The survey consisted of two tailored streams: one for OG respondents (19 questions) and one for experienced HEU MA project experts (12 questions).
- Background document from the "*Study on Outcomes Achieved by EIP-AGRI Operational Group Projects under the CAP* (EU CAP Network, June 2024)": to get everyone that will be participating in the workshop on the same ground, with relevant information about operational groups.
- Workshop, organised at 7th of April 2025, where different professionals from diverse areas discussed the results from the survey together with their own ideas about involving OGs in HEU.
- Final report: with all the ideas gathered from the survey, the workshop, previous work of PREMIERE project and validation sessions.

Figure 1: Process of developing the 3rd Focus Group within the PREMIERE project

For the survey, each PREMIERE project partner was responsible for sharing the questionnaire with individuals knowledgeable in either the field of OGs or HEU, resulting in a total of 124 responses. 47% from responded individuals were with experience in OGs.

A total of 23 participants joined the online workshop titled “*Operational Groups Go Horizon*”, representing a broad range of stakeholder categories and geographic regions. The participant selection aimed to reflect the diversity of actors involved in both EIP-AGRI OGs and HEU MAA projects and enabling representatives as NCP and European level organisations.

Discussion in the workshop was divided to 5 break-out groups (annex 4):

- Opening the door to Horizon Europe: Inclusion and Engagement for OG members;
- Resources, skills, capacities of OG members to engage in Horizon MA projects;
- Role of OG members in Horizon Project;
- Funding options for OG participation in Horizon Europe;
- Finding and aligning: How can OG members fit and be aligned in the HEU Call Topics?

For the final report, the PREMIERE team organised a validation round to make the material consistent with the work during the lifetime of the project. Participants and facilitators of the workshop brought together their expertise about the involvement of EIP-AGRI OGs in the HEU MA projects both as direct involvement and as enablers. The report combines also the results of the survey (including individual comments) and the related insights from “*Study on Outcomes Achieved by EIP-AGRI Operational Group Projects under the CAP*”.

3 DISCUSSION

The European Commission expects many more interactive innovation groups (incl OGs) from the grass-root level to be included in Horizon cluster 6 proposals. In the introduction of the HEU work programmes with the MAA as a eligibility condition, it is highlighted:

“To support the long-term vision for rural areas by 2040, it will help achieve thriving rural innovation ecosystems by supporting and/or establishing synergetic initiatives such as living labs, smart and start-up villages, European Innovation Partnership for Agriculture Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI) operational groups and a Thematic Smart Specialisation Platform.” (Cl6-2025 work programme, page 12)

The description of the MAA also refers explicitly to the involvement of OG and similar interactive innovation groups:

“For areas falling outside the remit of EIP-AGRI and CAP specific objectives, other similarly effective solutions ensuring dissemination at European level should be sought. Where appropriate, it is strongly recommended to involve interactive innovation groups such as the EIP-AGRI operational groups funded under the CAP.” (Cl6-2025, page 16)

The Focus Group process involved a variety of stakeholders engaged with this requirement of the work programme. Many voices were heard when they were asked to tell their success stories and share their concerns.

OGs have demonstrated themselves as a beneficial mechanism for fostering agricultural innovation across the European Union. Their practical, hands-on approach allows for the co-creation of solutions that directly address real-world farming and forestry challenges, producing tangible outcomes that contribute to sustainable agriculture and rural development¹.

However, despite these clear strengths and the interest among OG members to engage with broader research frameworks like Horizon Europe, this Focus Group identified several challenges that need to be tackled to optimize their impact and enable meaningful, long-term involvement in multi-actor projects.

Why Operational Groups should get involved in Horizon Europe?

- Ensure needs-driven research and innovation in Horizon projects and faster-spreading innovations.
- Address societal challenges using the Interactive Innovation Approach, while strengthening the AKIS.
- Elevate OG results to a European scale, adapt EU solutions to local contexts, and effectively disseminate innovation.

¹ "Study on Outcomes Achieved by EIP-AGRI Operational Group Projects under the CAP (EU CAP Network, June 2024)"

Focus Group participants agreed on the importance of strengthening connections between experienced HEU project teams and newcomers from interactive innovation initiatives, such as OGs. However, they emphasized that practical, legal, administrative, and communication barriers continue to hinder effective collaboration. A key issue raised was the lack of clear, practical guidance on how OGs should be involved in HEU proposals, particularly regarding the application of the MAA.

3.1 Administrative frameworks: overcoming legal and structural barriers

Current Horizon Europe guidelines and Cluster 6 work programme introductions do not sufficiently clarify **why EIP-AGRI Operational Groups should be engaged or how** they are expected to contribute to project outcomes. This lack of clarity leaves both OG members and experienced proposal coordinators in need of more detailed explanations regarding the purpose of the MAA and practical advice on how to involve local or newcomer interactive innovation groups. Despite these informational gaps, participants in the Focus Group recognized that the legal requirement to apply the MAA provides a valuable opportunity to increase the participation of actors from the farming, forestry, and rural business sectors in European research and innovation projects.

A critical systemic challenge is the current **lack of clarity in defining "OG involvement"** within official guidelines, which often creates confusion as to whether the participation of an entire OG consortium or only specific representatives is required. Involving an entire OG is regarded as practically impossible due their often not-legal formation. The use of generic terminology can mistakenly signal a level of complexity that deters practitioners, suggesting that the phrase should be replaced with "OG member involvement" to more accurately reflect realistic participation models. This functional definition ensures that practitioner contributions are integrated as a core part of the proposal's multi-actor methodology rather than being limited to passive consultation, which fails to satisfy the co-creation requirement of the MAA from

A critical systemic challenge is the **current lack of clarity in defining "OG involvement" within official guidelines**, which often creates confusion as to whether the participation of an entire Operational Group consortium or only specific representatives is required.

the beginning until the end of the project.

While administrative burdens and limited funding were frequently reported in the PREMIERE survey as primary challenges by OG members, discussions during the Focus Group workshop challenged the perception that HEU is uniquely burdensome. Experts noted that **Horizon Europe can be a more attractive funding format than many national programmes** because it includes prefunding and institutional overheads, which are often missing in Member State based funding schemes. Furthermore, recent regulatory changes have significantly improved accessibility for small and medium-sized enterprise owners who do not draw traditional salaries, suggesting that the perceived administrative weight of the program is often greater than the actual burden when compared to national CAP support.

A significant systemic obstacle to effective administration is the **structural separation between the support networks** for EIP-AGRI, such as the national CAP Network and Innovation Support Services, and those for HEU, such as the National Contact Points. These networks are managed by different national ministries with distinct objectives and target groups, which creates barriers to linking practical innovation on local levels with European Innovation Area. Improved coordination between these support structures is essential to help newcomers navigate the complex administrative and financial landscape, particularly for practitioners who face significant language barriers and a lack of specialized staff to manage English-based procedures during the project development phase.

Legal and administrative uncertainty further complicates the involvement of OGs, as many do not exist as formal legal entities and therefore cannot easily sign non-disclosure agreements or act as official project beneficiaries. To resolve these issues, there is a **critical need for clearer guidance on the different roles OG representatives can take**, such as acting as full partners, linked Third Parties or contractors providing good and services.

Funding laws and rules for projects differ between European programmes as well as between national funding frameworks. Administrative solutions available in Horizon funding might not be applicable in Interreg; and the Horizon framework legislation is different from regulations for Rural Development Programmes granting OG projects. However, the common rationale of the EIP-AGRI policy concepts connects both funding streams (HEU and OG, in this context) since 2014. For that reason, it would be helpful if the

guiding documents would refer to each other and help applicants to make connections. For example:

- Managing Authorities could take into account the timeline of EU-Horizon multi-actor projects, and could chose submission dates for OG applicants accordingly (e.g. after the publication of the next round of Cluster 6 calls).
- Managing Authorities could ask OG applicants to list potential alliances with projects that will be granted under particular Horizon multi-actor call topics to raise awareness of and request cooperation with upcoming EU-funded projects. Such a request could also apply to the search for ongoing Horizon projects and the acknowledgement if OG applicants participated as stakeholders in such thematically related EU-projects (Already now, OG applicants are requested to check EIP-AGRI archives and list OG projects with similar or related themes to avoid double funding).
- National research agencies in charge for the support of Horizon applicants can draft a funding measure for small organisations such as OG members, who aim to join Horizon proposal preparation.
- Already now, OG project applicants can include a capped budget position for EU-level activities such as travel to project conferences, Cluster 6 Info Days or Horizon brokerage events. Managing Authorities could change this option into a formal requirement. This will ensure that OG applicants to make use of the opportunity to engage in cross-border exchanges.

3.2 OG member experiences: challenges, insights, and lessons

Newcomers from grassroots organizations often enter HEU MA project consortia **without sufficient experience or understanding** of their potential roles, possibilities, restrictions and responsibilities within an EU-funded consortium. Drafting a project proposal needs excellent preparation, diligent analysis of the Call Topic(s) and good relationships for success. While members of OGs are confident in their technical skills², they frequently underestimate their possible contributions.

² Figure 5 of the study „Primary benefits of participation in EIP-AGRI OG“

This discrepancy between self-confidence of newcomers and the real value of their competencies for the MA proposal highlights a critical need for targeted guidance that empowers practice-oriented partners to assert their rights and secure meaningful roles during the consortium-building proposal writing process. Meanwhile, experienced proposal coordinators themselves often require support to transition from traditional research models to the co-creative MAA, ensuring that practitioners are integrated as core contributors³ rather than peripheral participants.

The demand for time and specialized staff or advice remains one of the most significant barriers to effective participation. Small business owners and decision-makers in non-governmental organizations often lack the capacity to contribute at the same intensity as dedicated proposal writing teams, leading to a structural disadvantage during the early stages of project development. This challenge is exacerbated by the current landscape of National Contact Point services, which often struggle to communicate effectively with practitioners from industry or grassroots backgrounds⁴. Consequently, many potential partners are hesitant to seek official support, creating a reliance on existing personal networks and hindering the inclusion of diverse, newcomer innovation groups.

Survey results highlight that **limited funding remains an obstacle for OG members**, who often lack the liquid resources to initiate new activities within the existing work planned in OG project workplan⁵.

³ Based on the survey, see free answers in the questionnaire, table 6.

⁴ Based on the survey, only 34% of the respondents (OG section) have received support from NCP or national/regional CAP network.

⁵ Financial rigidity and misalignment of OG and Horizon project cycles is a given. Each project needs to be financially managed following the particular rules. Moreover, an activity such as a field trial or soil testing can only be funded by one project. In contrast, it is foreseen that funding schemes complement each other and improve their impact through synergies in the best case.

The Commission does not expect OG members to contribute with unpaid work hours to Horizon projects when they highlight the sentence “OGs or other interactive innovation groups should be involved”. Instead, the Commission and its services are asking the evaluators to assess that all contributions and responsibilities to the multi-actor work plan are reflected appropriately in the budget. OG members joining Horizon project proposals need to deliver other goods or services than prepared for the OG project, and these additional work hours need to be remunerated appropriately by the Horizon project.

Beyond the structural constraints, there is a clear demand for fair financial compensation as foreseen by the European Commission' understanding of the MAA. The implementation of the MAA in EU-funded research and innovation projects expects the budget to include financial remuneration for practitioner actors such as OG members. Voluntary contribution is foreseen only for stakeholder involvement at a certain time (e.g. participation in a survey, workshop or seminar). The compensation needs to recognize practitioners as business owners rather than voluntary participants: farmers and small business owners must often hire external labour to cover their work while participating in research activities.

Liquidity is an issue for OG members because they have to cover OG expenses for around three month in advance. The full reimbursement of these costs comes after the end of the project only. Some OGs have to take a bank loan to allow the OG project to start. Under such circumstances, it is understandable OG members are reluctant or unable to invest even more money in project application, which might even never pay-off.

Language serves as both a literal and a conceptual barrier, as the dominance of English in official documentation can exclude valuable local knowledge and tacit insights. Beyond translation issues, a persistent disconnect exists between the technical terminology used in research and the practical language required for effective implementation on farms or in rural businesses.

To ensure genuine engagement rather than mere "tokenistic" inclusion to meet eligibility criteria, consortia must move beyond treating practitioners as simple source for data collection or dissemination purposes. Achieving this requires a fundamental shift in perspective, recognizing that the immediate, practical problem-solving focus of local groups must be synchronized with the longer, vision-oriented research timelines of European programs.

The sustainability of collaboration is often compromised by the loss of central contact persons and momentum once a specific OG project concludes⁶. Without a clear strategy for knowledge capitalization or long-term financial compensation for the time invested by practitioners in HEU proposal engagement, valuable innovations risk remaining at the pilot stage rather than

⁶ If the central contact person is not the research partner. Many OGs are coordinated by the usual suspects such as universities, advisory organisations, Chambers of Agriculture etc.

achieving widespread adoption. Operational Groups could be asked to submit a follow-up action plan, accompanied by a dedicated top-up budget to finance additional activities aimed at improving the exploitation and uptake of OG results. Establishing institutional links and providing fair remuneration for the expertise of business owners are essential steps toward creating a truly inclusive innovation ecosystem that values practical experience as much as scientific rigor. The MAA provides these opportunities. However, **advice and support on how** to plan for the practical and administratively robust involvement and remuneration of these valuable actors for research and innovation projects **is urgently needed**.

3.3 Proposal development practices: insights from experienced practitioners

The Focus Group revealed that HEU project partners in a leading position often lack the motivation and/or the competencies to facilitate co-creation processes among academic and non-academic project partners. However, when not all relevant actors contribute to the joint decision-making all along the duration of the project, the MAA will not be applied as expected. Such an incomplete implementation of co-innovation requirements results in the marginalization of small, practice-based actors. Consequently, their needs and practice-driven knowledge as well as their particular competencies will not enrich the project's output.

The willingness or ability to implement all MAA requirements is not always present among Horizon Europe project participants. This often results in a lack of interest or motivation to involve small practice-based actors in project planning and decision-making processes.

While visionaries explicitly recognize that OG coordinators possess unique facilitation skills that bridge the gap between science and practice (as well as technical competencies for testing and validating innovations) the practitioners themselves often underestimate their own potential impact beyond purely technical tasks. This internal hesitation is compounded by the strict administrative framework of the CAP and the dominance of the English language, which makes many OGs reluctant to engage at the European level. The strict financial administration of CAP funded projects contributes to OG

participants' reluctance to join Horizon projects and newcomers need individual support not only but also because of the language barrier.

From the perspective of proposal coordinators, **identifying and building trust with unfamiliar partners from grassroots backgrounds with possibly different interests and mindsets represents a significant challenge** compared to the perceived safety of established academic networks⁷. Consequently, there is a persistent tendency to favor long-standing scientific collaborations over the inclusion of new, potentially inexperienced practice-based partners who represent essential user perspectives.

Applying the MAA adds to the workload of intense demands for time and financial resources during the proposal development phase. Coordinators often prompt to finalize project plans without thorough consultation with practitioners, thereby undermining the co-creative intent of the MAA in an effort to save time.

Even experienced developers struggle with selecting the **most appropriate funding mechanisms for involving multiple practitioners** from the same region, whether they should be included as full consortium partners, other arrangements to involve actors or just as stakeholder. Those already deeply embedded in EU Research and Innovation (R&I) networks frequently overlook or fail to understand the specific barriers that newcomers, such as OG members, face when attempting to enter these specialized environments.

3.4 Outcomes from discussions

Focus Group participants highlighted a shared willingness to strengthen the connection between experienced Horizon project teams and newcomers from interactive innovation groups.

The synthesis of findings from the Focus Group reveals that while the MAA is intended to foster genuine co-innovation, a significant systemic disconnect remains between the operational reality of local practitioners and the strategic framework of European research.

⁷ Based on the survey, see free answers in the questionnaire, table 6.

- OGs are designed for rapid problem-solving, whereas HEU traditionally requires a long-term visionary commitment that often starts years before a project even begins. For many farmers and small business owners, this gap represents a barrier to entry that can only be bridged through targeted guidance.
- Although the multi-actor approach with the particular requirement to involve actors with practice orientation from the relevant industry in the core consortium of a Horizon-funded project, the practice actors still encounter traditional project governance without practitioner involvement on equal level with the academic partners. This experience of OG members highlight that the bottleneck for successful participation is the lack of recognition for practitioners as core contributors. Instead, proposal consortia often still only plan for classic stakeholder involvement for data collection, validation of results and dissemination/exploitation activities instead of taking the multi-actor requirements of co-creation from the beginning until the end of the project seriously.
- There is a need for a shift in the perceived definition of "OG involvement," moving away from the administratively impossible requirement of involving entire consortia toward the individual participation of motivated members who are granted a clear mandate and fair financial compensation for their time as business owners or individuals.
- The legal and institutional separation between national CAP networks and HEU National Contact Points prevents many OGs from accessing the specialized support they need to navigate complex funding landscapes.
- The successful integration of OG into the HEU ecosystem depends on building personal trust and "chemistry" within consortia. Strengthening the links between practice and research is not merely an administrative checkbox but a strategic necessity to ensure that European innovation is demand-driven, inclusive, and ready for real-world application. By addressing the structural barriers of language, funding alignment, and role clarity, the European Commission can unlock the full potential of its grassroots innovators to drive the transition toward a more resilient and sustainable agri-food sector.

Bridging the gap between local OGs and European research is like building a transcontinental railway; the project only succeeds when the heavy-duty rails of the strategic European framework are perfectly aligned with the locals with practical experience, ensuring that innovation can travel smoothly from the pilot station to widespread adoption.

4 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR HORIZON EUROPE

One of the most important recommendations for 2025 and 2026/2027 is to ensure that **evaluators** rigorously assess the application of the MAA in project proposals⁸. As long as evaluators do not score down application when practitioners' involvement only refers to classic stakeholder activities (workshops, surveys etc), the MAA eligibility condition will remain a 'toothless tiger'. Consistently applying this standard is the only way to signal to proposal writers that the MAA requires genuine attention rather than "tokenistic" inclusion where practitioners are added without meaningful roles. Proposals that do not comply with the Multi-Actor Eligibility Criterion should be rejected. Only when evaluators consistently apply this standard, all proposal writers will recognize the MAA's relevance and give it the attention it requires.

Clearer guidance is needed on the **options for involving OGs** in multi-actor consortia. To facilitate more effective engagement, official documentation must provide clear, practical examples of flexible involvement pathways, such as integrating individual motivated members of an OG rather than requiring an entire local consortium to navigate the legal complexities of joining as a single entity. The work programme and related documents should provide practical examples of how OGs or similar interactive innovation groups can be included, such as:

- Involving key OG members within a HEU project beneficiary's team, ensuring their knowledge feeds directly into the project.
- Including the OG coordination body or partner organisation as a full consortium member with clearly defined roles in implementation tasks like living labs, testing, or validation.

⁸ More details in the report of the Focus Group 2 „Advancing evaluation of the multi-actor approach (MAA)“ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17672414>

- Forming regional networks or sectoral clusters of member organisations of a particular OG will allow the involvement of all OG actors simultaneously in a HEU proposal consortium.
- Engaging OGs through Cascade Funding (FSTP, Financial Support for Third Parties) or contracts during the project phase, though this option should complement, not replace, practitioners' involvement from proposal development throughout the project and beyond.

To better support newcomers, tailored guidance on joining proposal consortia and accessing seed funding is essential. Building **long-term relationships** within European R&I networks is a key investment for individuals and organisations. Soft skills training can help prepare newcomers for collaboration in interdisciplinary teams, while better coordination between regional and European support structures would improve access, particularly concerning language and administrative barriers.

National and regional innovation services should extend their focus to facilitate OG participation in Horizon consortia. Brokerage events, international conferences, and targeted funding for OG representative's participation in scientific or networking events would enhance capacity building and foster partnerships. Successful outreach should prioritize peer-to-peer communication and the dissemination of success stories through relatable media to demonstrate the tangible benefits of participation to farmers and small business owners.

Financial accessibility remains a cornerstone of effective participation, necessitating the introduction of top-down mechanisms such as seed funding to support newcomers during the resource-intensive proposal development phase. It is also essential that practitioners are fairly compensated for their time as business owners, recognizing that their participation is a professional investment that should not be expected on a purely voluntary basis. Practical advice on strategically building European R&I relationships and securing seed funding for proposal contributions is crucial.

MAA has great potential

The MAA holds strong potential to accelerate the development and uptake of innovative solutions addressing societal and rural industry challenges. The European Commission's ambition, reflected in nearly 50% of Cluster 6 and Soil Mission topics requiring MAA, shows a clear commitment to involving

newcomer interactive innovation groups as equal partners in large R&I projects. Many stakeholders, including the PREMIERE team, share this commitment and believe in the co-creative power of this approach.

Recommendations to improve OG involvement in HEU proposals:

1. **Flexible participation and role flexibility.** Encouraging involvement of individual OG members rather than entire groups helps to bring the OG insights easily into European level. Allowing OG representatives to contribute to specific roles within HEU projects (without requiring full partnership status) helps maintain ongoing engagement despite the short lifespan of OGs.
2. **Provide administrative support.** Simplifying administrative procedures, is essential to making HEU more accessible to OG members, especially farmers. Multilingual support by national/regional enablers and streamlined regulations aligned with OGs' practical realities will reduce barriers to participation.
3. **Enhance awareness and tailored communication.** Increasing OG members' understanding of HEU through targeted, practical communication and clear guidance is crucial. By simplifying information and highlighting tangible benefits and success stories, OGs can be better motivated and equipped to engage meaningfully in HEU projects.
4. **Providing targeted advice and support.** Building stronger links and improved coordination between CAP Networks, Innovation Support Services, National Contact Points, and Horizon Europe actors will create a more cohesive support system. This collaboration will facilitate knowledge sharing, reduce fragmentation, and enable smoother OG integration into EU-level research initiatives

These three recommendations address the key structural, informational, and practical obstacles limiting OG participation and provide a strategic pathway toward more inclusive and effective engagement in HEU.

In conclusion, although OGs face several significant challenges, addressing these through targeted strategic communication, inclusive and flexible participation pathways, enhanced language and administrative support, improved coordination among relevant actors, and better use of existing

innovation networks will unlock their full potential. By bridging the gap between local practical innovation and EU-level research policies, OGs will continue to play a pivotal role in advancing sustainable agriculture and fostering rural development across Europe. Maximizing their contribution to HEU not only strengthens the innovation landscape but also contributes to the resilience and competitiveness of the agri-food sector in the context of evolving societal and environmental needs.

5 PREMIERE NEXT STEPS

This Focus Group was conducted within the framework of the PREMIERE project as part of a series of focus groups developed under Work Package 2. The plan is to conduct five additional focus groups, bringing the total to eight by the end of the project. To date, three focus groups have been organised:

- Focus Group 1: Programming MAA - “Challenges and solutions for more effective programming and implementation of the MAA”.
- Focus Group 2: Evaluating MAA – “Advancing evaluation of the multi-actor approach”.
- Focus Group 3: Operational Groups go Horizon – “Role and importance of EIP-AGRI Operational Groups in Horizon Europe Multi-Actor projects”.

The overall objective of these focus groups is to gather valuable insights that will inform the development of policy briefs. These contributions aim to improve the design and implementation of European projects and to enhance the conditions, participation, and learning outcomes for those involved in MA initiatives such as OGs and HEU projects.

6 ANNEXES

6.1 Annex I: Survey

In preparation for the workshop, a survey was disseminated in March 2025 to gather insights from key stakeholders involved in OG. The survey targeted two primary groups:

- Participants of OGs - 19 questions
- Experienced participants in HEU MA projects - 12 questions

To ensure that perspectives from both types of stakeholders were adequately captured, only one survey was used. However, it was structured to follow two distinct streams based on the respondent's experience. Specifically, the third question asked whether the respondent had participated in an OG. Depending on their answer, they were directed to one of two tailored question paths, as illustrated in the image below.

Figure 2: Example of the two different streams that the survey could take

A total of 124 survey responses were collected – 47% from individuals with experience in OGs and 53% from those without. This slight majority of non-OG participants suggests that, despite strong engagement with the EIP-AGRI instrument, many relevant stakeholders have yet to be involved.

Figure 3: Division of participation of the participants

The survey reflected broad geographic diversity, with most respondents from Spain (72%), followed by Poland (12%), and Ireland and France (9% each). Additional responses came from various other European countries, though in smaller numbers.

Cover letter: About the project

Subject: Help Shape the Future of Operational Groups in Europe!

Dear [Recipient's Name],

This survey is undertaken as part of the **PREMIERE** project funded under the EU 'Horizon Europe' (HEU) framework programme for research and innovation.

PREMIERE aims to strengthen the implementation of the Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) that is obligatory in approximately 40% of the HEU calls for projects on '**Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment**' (known as *Cluster 6*) plus the work programmes of the **Horizon Soil Mission** and the calls of **several Horizon Partnerships**. This includes those on Agroecology, Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking and associated programmes like PRIMA in the Mediterranean region.

The **specific version of the MAA** that is defined by DG AGRI for Cluster 6 and Horizon Soil Mission projects puts **into operation the 'interactive innovation model'**. This is an overarching open innovation concept that forms the basis of the EIP-AGRI and revolves around three main principles: (1) developing

innovative solutions focusing on farmers/foresters needs; (2) collaboration between various actors to make best use of complementary types of knowledge (scientific, practical, organisational, etc.) targeted to project objectives; and (3) co-creation and diffusion of solutions/opportunities ready to implement in practice.

These principles are applied at different scales in BOTH **CAP-funded EIP-AGRI Operational Group (OG) projects** and the **various Horizon MAA projects** that contribute to the EIP-AGRI. However, they are programmed slightly differently according to the two different funding regimes. It is the **ambition of the European Commission to better connect** CAP-funded OG projects and Horizon-funded MAA projects. Therefore, in the current definition of the MAA it is “strongly recommended that relevant interactive innovation groups, such as EIP-AGRI Operational Groups funded under the CAP, become involved”. The question is – **how best** to pursue this recommendation?

About the survey

We invite you to participate in this survey, which aims to assess the role and importance of representatives of the European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (**EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (OG)**) in **Horizon Europe** projects adopting a **Multi-Actor Approach (MAA)**.

Objective of the survey: Evaluate the role of **EIP-AGRI OGs** in Horizon Europe projects using **MAA**.

The following survey is addressed to:

1. OGs coordinators, and participants.
2. Horizon project coordinators and partners, with or without connection to OGs.

Importance of the **MAA**:

1. It refers to an **interactive, transdisciplinary, and responsible** research and innovation (R&I) process.
2. Designed to enhance **co-creation for innovation**.
3. Ensuring outcomes are **co-owned, reliable, demand-driven, and relevant to address societal challenges**.

Importance of EIP-AGRI OGs:

- Represent key players in **connecting innovation with practical application.**
- Are **currently underrepresented** in Horizon Europe projects although the OG funding rationale and the Horizon Multi-Actor projects form the two areas of the overarching EIP-AGRI concept since more than a decade already.
- And Horizon project consortia are facing various **challenges** in effectively integrating the contributions of the OG members.

Your input will feed into a focus group discussion with a mixed group of actors from OG projects, Horizon projects and representatives of the EU Commission and its services. Together with the analysis of the survey data, the results will feed into the development of recommendations on how the challenges faced by EIP-AGRI OGs in MAA projects can be addressed. Your responses are key to shaping recommendations for better collaboration and Multi-Actor project outcomes.

This survey is open for contributions **until 20th of March.**

Thank you for your valuable input!

For more information about the project, please visit the following website:

<https://premiere-multiactor.eu/>

All information about the Focus Group and the survey will be available at the provided link to the website once the Focus Group has concluded.

General information for the survey

Section 1: General information	
1. Which of the following key stakeholder groups across policy, research and practice do you represent?	- Government/Policy - Science/Academia - Industry/Business - Society/Community
2. In which country is your organization based?	
3. Are you currently, or have you been in the past, a partner of an EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (OGs)?	Yes No

Table 2: Basic information for both streams of the survey

Operational Groups

Section 2: Involvement and participation in Operational Groups	
4. In how many EIP-AGRI OGs have you been involved?	One Two to four Five or more
5. What was the grant amount for your most recent EIP-AGRI OG project?	< 100.000 € 100.000 € – 199.999 € 200.000 € – 399.999 € 400.000 € – 599.999 € 600.000 € – 1.000.000 € > 1 Million € Not sure / prefer not to answer
6. What is/was the focus area of your EIP-AGRI OG(s)?	Agricultural productivity Sustainability Environmental impacts Socio-economic impacts Food supply chain Climate and climate change Research & Innovation Forestry Digitalisation AKIS Jobs, growth and equality in rural areas
7. How would you characterise your most recent or ongoing OG project?	Technical development project (low TLR)

	<p>Technical piloting project (medium TLR)</p> <p>Marketing/sales project (high TLR)</p> <p>Value chain project</p> <p>Networking project</p> <p>Communication/dissemination project</p> <p>Co-creation and co-learning project</p> <p>Social innovation project</p> <p>Environmental protection project</p> <p>Other</p>
7.1. If you selected "Other", please specify:	
8. How would you rate your experience with the most recent EIP-AGRI OG?	(Scale from 1 to 5)
9. What has been the primary benefit of participating in your last EIP-AGRI OGs?	<p>Knowledge Exchange</p> <p>Networking opportunities</p> <p>Access to funding</p> <p>Implementation of new products and/or methodologies</p> <p>Identification of challenges and new opportunities</p> <p>Development and testing of technical innovation</p> <p>Other</p>
9.1. If you selected "Other", please specify:	
10. What challenges have you encountered while participating in EIP-AGRI OGs?	<p>Limited funding to fulfil the foreseen work</p> <p>Budget constraints from the outset</p> <p>Lack of involvement in decision-making processes by the leading team(s)</p> <p>Lacking skills, competent staff and/or own time to engage</p> <p>Insufficient technical and other resources</p> <p>Administrative burdens</p> <p>Other</p>
10.1. If you selected "Other", please specify:	
11. At which level has your EIP-AGRI OGs networked with others?	<p>Regional</p> <p>National</p>

	Transnational Not sure / prefer not to answer
Section 3: Interaction with Horizon Europe projects	
12. Have you participated in a Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe Multi-Actor project?	Yes No
12.1. If yes, has this EU project involved any EIP-AGRI OG members?	Yes No
12.2. What was the role of the EIP-AGRI OG representative(s) in the project?	
12.3. EIP-AGRI OGs typically have no legal entity by themselves, so how did you formalise the participation in the Horizon proposal and project?	
13. Has your national / regional CAP Network or Horizon National Contact Point provided you with any information / advice in participating in Horizon Europe?	Yes No
13.1. Please specify the information you received from the National Contact Point:	
14. In your opinion, how can EIP-AGRI OG representatives best contribute to Horizon Europe projects?	Providing test sites for Research and Innovation activities Contributing innovative solutions and results developed by the OG project Acting as key implementation partners Facilitating knowledge transfer between research and practice Supporting dissemination of learnings at the local or regional level Providing practical insights that address real-world challenges Other
14.1. If you selected "Other", please specify:	
15. Which role do you think EIP-AGRI OG members should take in Horizon Europe projects?	Leader / Coordinator Partner / Beneficiary Third-party / Associated partner Contractor/Subcontractor

	<p>Advisory board member, Ambassador etc.</p> <p>Stakeholder</p> <p>Other</p>
15.1. If you selected "Other", please specify:	
16. What barriers do you see in integrating EIP-AGRI OG representatives into Horizon Europe project consortia?	<p>Lack of awareness</p> <p>Insufficient human resources</p> <p>Misaligned goals</p> <p>Complex administrative processes</p> <p>Lack of access to information on existing opportunities</p> <p>Other</p>
16.1. If you selected "Other", please specify:	
17. What support would help EIP-AGRI OG actors to be more effective in their roles when engaging in Horizon Europe proposal or project activities?	<p>Additional funding for personnel</p> <p>Training in financial administration and other legal requirements</p> <p>More networking opportunities with OGs and experts</p> <p>Better access to data, tools, and digital platforms</p> <p>Other</p>
17.1. If you selected "Other", please specify:	
18. Which good practices have you observed in successful EIP-AGRI OGs?	<p>Facilitation of the work within the OG</p> <p>Facilitating stakeholder collaboration (e.g. between practice and research)</p> <p>Providing practical insight and local expertise to academic partners and stakeholders</p> <p>Peer-to-peer learning</p> <p>Testing/piloting of innovative solutions and demonstrations</p> <p>Involving all project partners in project work and associated decision-making processes</p> <p>Ensuring well-targeted dissemination</p> <p>Other</p>
18.1. If you selected "Other", please	

specify:	
Section 4: Feedback and recommendations	
19. Do you have any additional comments or suggestions for improving the effectiveness of EIP-AGRI OG projects and the involvement of OG representatives in EU Horizon Multi-Actor projects?	

Table 3: All the questions for the OG survey stream

Horizon Europe project

Section 2: Involvement and participation	
4. Have you participated in one or more Horizon Europe/Horizon 2020 project(s)?	Yes No
4.1. If you selected "Yes", please specify your role(s):	Leader / Coordinator Partner / Beneficiary Third-party / Associated partner Contractor/Subcontractor Advisory board member, Ambassador etc. Stakeholder Other
4.2. If you selected "Other", please specify:	
4.3. What have been the three most important benefits of participating in Horizon projects?	Increased visibility Capacity Building Involvement in research and innovation Networking opportunities Access to funding Implement new products and methodologies Other
4.4. If you selected "Other", please specify:	
5. Has your organization participated in a Horizon project with the mandatory application of the Multi-Actor Approach (MAA)?	Yes No I do not know
6. If your organization has participated in a Horizon Europe (HE) project, did the project involve any EIP-AGRI Operational Group (OG)	Yes No

actors?	
6.1. If you selected "Yes", please specify their role(s):	
7. Were you directly involved in integrating the EIP-AGRI OG into the project?	Yes No
7.1. If you selected "Yes", please specify how:	
Section 3: Interaction with Horizon Europe projects	
8. How do you think EIP-AGRI Operational Groups can best contribute to Horizon Europe projects?	<p>Providing practical insights that address real-world challenges</p> <p>Contributing innovative solutions and results developed by the OG project</p> <p>Acting as key implementation partners</p> <p>Facilitating knowledge transfer between research and practice</p> <p>Supporting dissemination of learnings at the local or regional level</p> <p>Providing test sites for research and innovation activities</p> <p>Other</p>
8.1. If you selected "Other", please specify:	
9. Do you believe integrating EIP-AGRI OG members into Horizon Europe projects could improve project outcomes?	(Scale from 1 to 5)
10. What barriers do you see in integrating OG representatives into Horizon Europe projects?	<p>Lack of awareness</p> <p>Lacking staff</p> <p>Misaligned goals</p> <p>Access to resources and expertise needed</p> <p>Usually, OGs have no legal entity</p> <p>Lack of connection and information on how to find the best OGs for a proposal</p> <p>Insufficient competencies</p> <p>Other</p>
10.1. If you selected "Other", please specify:	
11. Which good practices have you observed in successful EIP-AGRI OGs?	Facilitation of the work within the OG

	Facilitating stakeholder collaboration (e.g. between practice and research) Providing practical insight and local expertise to academic partners and stakeholders Peer-to-peer learning Testing/piloting of innovative solutions and demonstrations Involving all project partners in project work and associated decision-making processes Ensuring well-targeted dissemination Other
11.1. If you selected "Other", please specify:	
Section 4: Feedback and recommendations	
12. Do you have any additional comments or suggestions for improving the effectiveness of EIP-AGRI OGs on the national/local level and on the level of Horizon EU Multi-Actor projects?	

Table 5: All the questions for the HEU survey stream

6.1.1 Outcomes from the Operational Groups survey

The OG stream was answered by a total of 58 participants this represents a 46% of the total answers.

Nearly half of the respondents (48%) reported involvement in five or more OGs, indicating a high level of experience. The remaining respondents were evenly split between those involved in one OG (26%) and those in two to four OGs (26%).

Figure 4: Participation in OGs

Participants most frequently identified the development and testing of technical innovations, followed by implementing new products and methodologies, as the main benefits of their OG involvement. Knowledge exchange was also valued, while networking, funding access, and identifying new opportunities were seen as less significant.

Figure 5: Primary benefits of participation in EIP-AGRI OG

The most commonly reported challenges in EIP-AGRI OGs were administrative burdens and limited funding to carry out planned activities. These findings underscore that financial and administrative issues are the primary barriers to effective OG participation.

Figure 6: Challenges encountered in EIP-AGRI OG

Almost half of the participants engaged with two to four Operational Groups, while fewer than a quarter participated in five or more. Most rated their experience with their most recent OG as “Very Good” or “Excellent”, reflecting high satisfaction with the projects.

Figure 7: Rating of the experience with OGs

In order to get a scale of the projects of the participants the following question was asked ‘What was the grant amount for your most recent EIP-AGRI OG project?’. Where most of the answer said between 100.000 € - 199.999€, which would be an average grant money for an operational group, this one is followed by ‘200.000€ - 399.999€’, which was a close second. As it can be seen in the following graph:

Figure 8: Challenges encountered by OGs

The pie chart shows that agricultural productivity is the primary focus of EIP-AGRI OGs at 29%, followed by climate change (17%) and research and innovation (14%). Other areas like sustainability, food supply chain, socio-economic impacts, digitalisation, and environmental impacts also receive notable attention, highlighting diverse priorities.

Figure 9: Focus area of the OG

Other important information was the role that the participants of OG should take when participating in HE projects; the results were what was expected. A great majority participated as ‘Partner/Beneficiary’, at a lower grade there was ‘Stakeholder’ and then ‘Leader/coordinator’.

Figure 10: Primary benefits of participating in OGs

The bar chart shows that the most common role OG members see themselves in Horizon Europe projects is "Partner/Beneficiary" (49 responses), followed by "Stakeholder" (22) and "Leader/Coordinator" (14). Other roles like "Advisory board member" and "Contractor/Subcontractor" received fewer responses.

Figure 11: Support needed by OG actors

The following bar chart about the support that OG actors would find more effective shows that the most frequently selected type of support was "Additional funding for personnel", with 43 responses. This was followed by "More networking opportunities with OGs and experts" (24), "Training in

financial administration and other requirements" (23), and "Better access to data, tools, and digital platforms" (15).

Figure 12: Role that OG members should take in HE projects

The majority of EIP-AGRI Operational Groups reported networking at the regional level (41), followed by national (22) and transnational (6) levels. This highlights a strong local focus with limited cross-border collaboration.

Figure 13: Levels of networking among EIP-AGRI OG

The following pie chart presents the responses to the question of whether participants have taken part in a Horizon 2020 or HEU Multi-Actor project. The results show a nearly even split, with 52% of respondents indicating they have not participated in such projects, while 48% reported that they have.

Have you participated in a Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe Multi-Actor project?

Figure 14: Participation in Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe MAA projects

Comments from Operational Groups survey

In the final section of the OG survey, participants had the opportunity to leave comments. The question posed was: “Do you have any additional comments or suggestions for improving the effectiveness of EIP-AGRI OG projects and the involvement of OG representatives in EU Horizon Multi-Actor projects?”

Below are the comments received.

Comments from Operational Groups survey
“Implement the needs related to food security and the sustainability of the food production chain.”
“It would be interesting to have the full time allocated in the schedule available at the moment of applying for the project (without time cuts for project execution).”
“Although I believe I have already mentioned it, one of the main obstacles is excessive bureaucracy and the lack of flexibility in allocating resources to the real needs of the projects.”
“We believe that Operational Groups (OGs) have significant potential to create a strong impact on EU Horizon projects, and efforts should be made to bridge the gap between the two programs. The pilot tests carried out in our regional OGs should be better disseminated and supported if there is a connection with Horizon Europe. “
“In my experience with OGs, participating companies are usually small and lack the personnel and time to dedicate to research, development, and/or innovation projects. They need clear, easily accessible, and easy-to-understand information about calls and administrative procedures.”
“Additionally, they do not have sufficient financial resources to start activities. They would need to receive funding at the beginning of the project; currently, in OGs, funds are only received after activities are completed and all justification documents are submitted.”
“A major obstacle is bureaucracy and official audits, which treat each project as a closed System.”
“Financial support for EIP-AGRI OG projects is generally more rewarding than for EU Horizon

Multi-Actor projects. The results often surpass those obtained in EU Horizon projects, which are difficult to prepare and, if approved, challenging to manage.”
“Sustainability (both environmental and social) is a crucial issue to address, and we try to incorporate it into our projects. However, in some technical projects, it is difficult to receive a good evaluation because the impact on the environment and society is hard to measure. Conducting a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) or using other indicators would require significant project resources.”
“Encouragement and implementation of simple tools to improve collaboration between projects.”
“Consider that OGs exist for a very limited time, making it difficult to align with Horizon Europe projects.”
“EIP OGs and Horizon groups tend to involve different types of actors, making the transition from EIP to Horizon projects complex.”
“For EU-level projects, the English language often becomes a barrier. This means that farmers who could contribute valuable knowledge and ideas may stay away, leading to missed opportunities for innovation and experience-sharing.”
“Discussion, knowledge exchange, skills sharing, and getting to know each other.”
“The justification process for EIP-AGRI OG projects is excessively detailed, requiring attendance records, minutes, pictures, and work facts that focus on quantity rather than real results or the quality of interactions. Even for subcontracted research institutes, bureaucracy has become overwhelming compared to the benefits obtained.”
“Engaging farmers, cooperative associations, or companies from the agri-forest sectors in EU projects is not difficult if they understand the learning opportunities for them. They should receive a higher funding rate, not necessarily for personal compensation but in ways that provide tangible benefits. Having a pre-established relationship with such partners is highly beneficial.”
“One aspect that is not well addressed in the multi-actor approach is dealing with open data, GDPR, and intellectual and industrial property rights. These topics are not common in the agricultural sector or even in R&D academia. There is a lack of guidance on these issues when preparing proposals and during project implementation.”
“While communication and dissemination experts have been incorporated into projects, and scientists have developed communication skills, they cannot also be expected to be legal experts. The European Commission does not provide sufficient support or place enough emphasis on these aspects.”

Table 4: Reflections from OG stream

6.1.2 Outcomes from the Horizon Europe projects survey

In this section are the participants that haven't participated in OGs, and answer the survey as HE project participants with experience. A total of 66 participants answered this section of the survey, this represents a 53% of the total answers.

The most valued benefits of participating in Horizon Europe projects were "Involvement in research and innovation", "Access to funding", and "Networking opportunities", with research and innovation ranked highest. These results reflect participants focus on active engagement and resource access in collaborative projects.

Figure 15: Key benefits of participating in Horizon projects

The bar chart presents responses to the question: "Do you believe integrating EIP-AGRI OG members into Horizon Europe projects could improve project outcomes?". The majority of respondents expressed agreement, with 29 selecting "Agree" and 14 selecting "Strongly Agree". Eleven respondents were "Neutral", while only a small number disagreed, 2 selected "Disagree" and 1 selected "Strongly Disagree".

Figure 16: Perception of the impact of integrating EIP-AGRI members on Horizon Europe project outcomes

The bar chart presents responses to the question: "Has your organization participated in a Horizon project with the mandatory application of the Multi-Actor Approach (MAA)?" The majority of respondents (44) answered "Yes", indicating prior participation. Ten respondents indicated "No", while 12 selected "I do not know".

Figure 17: Participation in Horizon projects applying the MAA

The graph shows that "Coordinator/Leader" and "Partner/Beneficiary" are the most common and involved roles in Horizon Europe projects. Other roles like "Board of Experts" and "Third Party" have significantly less participation, highlighting a concentration in leadership and partnership positions.

Figure 18: Project involvement and role in Horizon Europe

The bar chart shows that most respondents answered "No" to whether their Horizon Europe projects involved Operational Group actors, with fewer answering "Yes." This indicates limited OG involvement in HE projects and highlights a need for greater collaboration in the future.

Figure 19: Involvement of EIP-AGRI Operational Groups in Horizon Europe projects

Comments from Horizon Europe survey

In the final section of the HE survey, participants had the opportunity to leave comments.

The question posed was: “Do you have any additional comments or suggestions for improving the effectiveness of EIP-AGRI OGs on the national/local level and on the level of Horizon EU Multi-Actor projects?”

Below are the comments received.

Comments from Horizon Europe survey
“More interaction between applied research projects and OGs, as these allow advancements to be brought down to the field.”
“Reduce bureaucracy / evaluate the RESULTS of projects 2 and 5 years later / acknowledge that the Mediterranean exists and is unlike any other countries in the EU / prioritize reality over virtuality in project selection / facilitate personnel contracts between countries / reject all projects that include terms like ‘sustainability, AI, words ending in ‘omics,’ efficiency...’ without proper context in their wording / value sobriety in solutions, as well as common sense and empathy in their application.”
“Need to call OG to participate in larger projects; these need to show usability and realist approaches.”
“Regarding questions 3 and 6, our organization has participated in several projects on H2020 and Horizon Europe in which I have not personally participated, therefore the possibility of involving EIP-AGRI OGs may have happened without my involvement.”
“The competition of project proposals makes it difficult to have an OG and HE MAA the same time with the same thematic. Or the scope is too broad that the cooperation is only superficial. In projects, the KPIs are very high, to become granted (get the funding). Therefore, deep connections with other projects, or searching for interesting links with other projects is often difficult, because you are so ‘into’ your own project and KPIs. For example, joint events - who will claim the costs? Can an audit ‘punish’ us if the rules (that are complex, lots of administration, regulations) were misinterpreted? This is a stressor for me (personally).”
“The group should be expanded with new participants to enrich the approach and ensure a more comprehensive analysis of project needs and challenges. Given the diversity of issues that arise, a more structured and results-oriented plan is necessary. To effectively reach a multidisciplinary actor approach, dedicated groups should be established for different needs, allowing for a more targeted and effective response. This will help address challenges more closely and ensure the project’s success at both national and Horizon EU levels.”
“We should consider involving identified actors as partners of consortiums and not only work with them as stakeholders.”
“Cross border Operational Groups.”
“This needs involvement of OGs at the pre-proposal stage”
“OGs must be easier to discover and reach!”
“Mentoring after and before the creation of the OG, foment knowledge exchange between countries (maybe with neighbour countries work more easily), lessons learned, failures are more relevant than successful cases, thematic workshops, farm and forest demos, etc.”
“EIP-AGRI OGs could contact project coordinators to present their services and knowledge for a better collaboration. A guide for the MAA would be great, beyond the HE webinars.”
“Frequently the OGs have a different temporal development compared to HE projects, which makes complicated to work with them. They have normally a “strict” work plan, with financial constraints posed by the funding authority (for example, the obligation of spending 60% of budget for staff, which sometime is not necessary). This makes difficult for them (and the HE project) to widen or introduce new common activities.”
“National language to reach practitioners seems important / focus on practical outcomes / low administrative workload / value their work through communication.”
“OGs are totally unfamiliar to me, don’t know how they are funded, organised, and for what purpose. Can only derive from the intro text and the questions they may be something similar

to Living Labs? But maybe with a more long-term funding? So first barrier to including them in Horizon projects, make them known at all.”
“EIP-AGRI OGs should be recognisable as an entity, or at least a legal representative must be appointed in order to facilitate their collaboration with Horizon projects. For example, if there is no legal representative, who can sign the non-disclosure agreements which are crucial for the dissemination of innovations? Who is appointed to participate (be reimbursed for) travels or dissemination events of the project?”
“A list of contacts would help with specific specializations and expertise. Links to policy-making bodies could be a role that the OGs could take on. This way they may help increase a project's impact.”
“EIP-Agri OGs that have no funding vanish quickly. In a project-work-based world the projects die once the final report is submitted. EC needs a long time strategy for EIP-agri OGs.”

Table 6: Reflections from Horizon Europe survey

6.1.3 Common questions: Operational Groups vs. Horizon Europe

The bar chart compares how OG and HE respondents view OG contributions to Horizon Europe projects. Both groups prioritized “Facilitating knowledge transfer between research and practice,” with HE respondents also valuing practical insights and dissemination, while OG respondents highlighted providing test sites and serving as implementation partners.

Figure 20: Perceived contributions of EIP-AGRI OG to HE projects (comparison of OG and HE survey responses)

The bar chart shows that the top barriers to integrating EIP-AGRI Operational Groups into Horizon Europe consortia are complex administrative processes and insufficient human resources. Other notable obstacles include misaligned goals, lack of awareness, and limited access to information on opportunities.

Figure 21: Comparison of perceived barriers to integrating EIP-AGRI into HE consortia

The bar chart highlights that the top good practices in successful OGs are “facilitating stakeholder collaboration” and “testing innovative solutions”. Providing practical local expertise to academic partners is also widely recognized as important.

Figure 22: Good practices observed in successful EIP-AGRI OGs, based on OG and HE survey responses

6.2 Annex 2: Background paper

PREMIERE Focus Group 'OGs go Horizon' April 2025

Background Paper: The Role and Impact of EIP-AGRI Operational Groups in European Agricultural Innovation

1. Introduction:

Operational Groups (OGs) under the European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI) play a pivotal role in fostering innovation within the agricultural and rural sectors of the European Union. By bringing together farmers, researchers, advisors, and businesses, OGs serve as a collaborative platform for developing practical and innovative solutions to agricultural challenges.

This background paper provides an overview of the key findings from the "Study on Outcomes Achieved by EIP-AGRI Operational Group Projects under the CAP" (EU CAP Network, June 2024). It highlights the importance of OGs, the impact they have had so far, the challenges they face, and recommendations for enhancing their effectiveness within the EU's agricultural policy framework.

2. The Importance of Operational Groups:

OGs have been instrumental in bridging the gap between research and agricultural practice. Their significance lies in:

- **Encouraging Interactive Innovation:** OGs enable farmers and researchers to co-develop solutions that are both practical and scientific.
- **Addressing Key Agricultural Challenges:** These include climate change adaptation, resource efficiency, biodiversity conservation, and digitalization in agriculture.
- **Enhancing Knowledge Exchange:** OGs facilitate the transfer of knowledge between research institutions and farmers, ensuring that innovation reaches end-users effectively.
- **Strengthening Rural Economies:** By promoting entrepreneurship and collaborative projects, OGs contribute to rural development and job creation.

3. Key Findings from the EU CAP Network Study:

According to the study, OGs have successfully contributed to:

- **Technology Adoption:** Many OG projects have led to the development and implementation of innovative farming techniques and technologies.
- **Sustainability and Environmental Benefits:** Projects focused on soil health, water conservation, and biodiversity protection have delivered positive environmental outcomes.
- **Policy Impact:** Some OG projects have influenced national and regional policies by providing data and recommendations for sustainable agricultural practices.

However, the study also highlights differentiation in the performance and impact of OGs across EU Member States, largely due to differences in funding structures, administrative support, and national CAP Strategic Plans.

4. Challenges Facing Operational Groups:

Despite their successes, OGs encounter several obstacles that limit their full potential, as mentioned in Funding Distribution of OGs Across the EU (extracted from the study):

- **Limited Funding and Administrative Complexity:** Many OGs struggle with securing adequate funding and navigating bureaucratic hurdles.
- **Difficulties in Scaling Up Innovations:** While OGs develop innovative solutions, transitioning from pilot projects to widespread adoption remains challenging.
- **Fragmentation and Lack of Coordination:** The study finds that stronger connections between OGs and Horizon Europe projects are needed to maximize synergies.
- **Regulatory Barriers:** Variability in CAP implementation across Member States creates divergences in how OGs operate and receive support.

5. Recommendations for Strengthening OGs:

To enhance the effectiveness and long-term impact of OGs, the study suggests:

- **Increased Financial and Policy Support:** Simplifying funding mechanisms and ensuring long-term financial sustainability is crucial.
- **Improved Collaboration with Horizon Europe:** Establishing structured links between OGs and EU-funded research projects would enhance knowledge-sharing and innovation diffusion.
- **Better Dissemination Strategies:** Enhancing outreach efforts to ensure that OG-generated knowledge reaches a broader audience.
- **Harmonized CAP Implementation:** Greater consistency in how CAP supports OGs across Member States would create a more balanced playing field.

6. Conclusion:

Operational Groups have proven to be a key mechanism for fostering agricultural innovation in the EU. However, addressing the challenges outlined in the study is essential for maximizing their impact. By strengthening financial support, fostering collaboration with Horizon Europe, and ensuring streamlined administrative processes, OGs can continue to drive meaningful advancements in sustainable agriculture and rural development.

This background paper is based on the "Study on Outcomes Achieved by EIP-AGRI Operational Group Projects under the CAP" (EU CAP Network, June 2024).

6.3 Annex 3: Workshop participants

As previously mentioned, two main activities involved external stakeholders: the survey and the workshop. Different actors participated in each activity.

The selection of participants was carried out with the aim of ensuring balanced representation across stakeholder groups and countries. For the survey, each PREMIERE partner distributed the questionnaire to individuals they considered relevant and knowledgeable. There was no limit to the number of respondents, as a higher response rate was expected to enhance objectivity and representativeness, resulting in a total of **124 responses**.

In contrast, participation in the workshop was more selective. To ensure effective discussion and engagement, the number of participants was limited to a maximum of 25. Following the selection process, team sent out invitation emails to ensure clarity and encourage participation. After completing the registration, participants received a confirmation email including the meeting agenda, date, and link to join the online session. **A total of 23 participants joined** the online workshop titled “*Operational Groups Go Horizon*”, representing a broad range of stakeholder categories and geographic regions. The participant selection aimed to reflect the diversity of actors involved in both EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (OGs) and Horizon Europe Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) projects.

Gender was taken into account during the participant selection process for the workshop, with the objective of ensuring balanced and inclusive representation. As a result, the final composition of the workshop reflected a strong female presence, with 80% of participants identifying as women and 20% as men.

The workshop was looking for different categories, so most of the different areas involving European projects and operational groups were participating. The workshop ended up with the following categories:

Operational group practitioners and implementers

- Farmers, Agricultural Cooperatives, Private Sector, and Agri-Tech Companies with OG involvement
- EIP-AGRI Operational Group Coordinators

- OG involved in Horizon Europe Multi-Actor project

These carry out the activities and coordinate them, so the profiles represent actors directly involved in the implementation of Operational Groups (OG)

Research and Horizon coordination experts

- Researchers and Academics with Horizon involvement
- Horizon Coordinators of Thematic Networks with OGs
- PREMIERE Partner with Experience in Operational Groups

These groups bring research experience.

Policy Makers, NCPs, and EU Representatives

Support and outreach organisations

- Advisory Services and Extension Agents working with OGs
- NGOs and Rural Development Organizations with OG involvement

These groups facilitate the work of OG through education, outreach or support, their role is enabling, not executing.

Total of 23 participants contributed to the workshop		
Actor groups	N° of participants	% of all participants
Operational group practitioners and implementers	7	30%
Research and Horizon coordination experts	3	13%
Policy Makers, NCPs, and EU Representatives	9	39%
Support and outreach organizations	4	17%
PREMIERE facilitating team	Shane Conway (University of Galway) Albert Escola, Lluc Tost (DARPA) Hanna Tamsalu, Konstantin Mihhejev (METK) Susanne von Münchhausen (HNEE) Pierre Rochepeau (ARVALIS) Mark Redman, Jordi Pietx (HCC) Vesna Milicic, Zala Plateis (CCIS-CAFE)	

Table 7: List of participants by actor groups

Participants came from across Europe, ensuring a wide territorial perspective. The most represented region was the ‘Atlantic’ (8 participants), followed by the

‘European Commission’ (7). Then it came the ‘Mediterranean’ (5), followed by the ‘Baltic’ region (2), and then ‘Danube’ (1).

Limitations

While this Focus Group provided valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities surrounding the involvement of Operational Groups in Horizon Europe projects, several limitations should be acknowledged.

Participant Scope: Despite efforts to ensure balanced stakeholder representation, not all areas of expertise were represented. For example, some categories, such as Operational Groups involved in Horizon Europe projects, were underrepresented, which may limit the general visibility of conclusions.

Survey Response Diversity: The survey responses used to inform the Focus Group workshop discussion, while valuable, were concentrated in a few countries (e.g., Spain), potentially skewing regional perspectives.

6.4 Annex 4: Workshop Outcomes

The workshop was divided into a plenary session and then five different breakout rooms, this following section will analyse each of the themes of discussion.

6.4.1 Plenary session for the Focus Group workshop

The workshop was opened with a brief overview of the PREMIERE project, followed by an interactive Mentimeter icebreaker where participants shared their expertise and expectations. The PREMIERE overview presentation can be found on annex 4, and the Mentimeter responses can be found on the 5th annex. This was followed by a presentation of the pre-session survey results (annex 1), which highlighted key challenges Operational Groups face within the Horizon Europe landscape and set the stage for the discussions.

When asked to describe OGs in one word, participants highlighted terms like "innovation," "cooperative," and "collaboration," though some also noted "chaos". Based the survey, a significant disconnect was revealed: Horizon experts believe OGs lack access to information, while OG members find the administrative processes too complex to navigate.

During the session the “myth” that Horizon Europe is uniquely burdensome was challenged, as it appears to be easier to administer as a project beneficiary than other national programs (incl CAP support). Rather than being a burden, Horizon Europe can be described as an attractive funding format because it includes prefunding and "overhead" for institutions (which national funding often lacks). Recent regulatory changes have made the HEU program more accessible for SME owners without salaries.

Participants highlighted, that the number of OGs per country differs significantly. The reason may hinder behind administrative reasons e.g number of calls, scope of funding and other funding possibilities for similar actions; but it may be the reason of person’s willingness and courage. HEU possibilities are growing to be more attractive as national (or Member State based) funding scope is going down and several occasions were noted that scientific partners of OG “grow” into HEU.

A recurring theme was the "scientific language" barrier. Practitioners often struggle to translate strategic descriptions into practical applications. It was observed that the success of OGs often depends on enthusiastic individuals and effective advisory systems rather than just national regulations.

6.4.2 'Opening the door to Horizon Europe: inclusion and engagement for OG members'

1. *Limited awareness and disconnection from HE structure*

Participants highlighted that while many OGs express interest in Horizon Europe (HE), several practical and perceptual barriers limit their involvement. While OGs may have resources during their lifespan, they often lack the time, and once the project ends, they have time but no resources, making further engagement with HE difficult.

Operational Groups (OGs) often lack awareness of Horizon Europe and face structural mismatches, as their short-term, practical focus contrasts with HE's long-term research orientation. Limited time, resources, and continuity mechanisms, combined with unclear support pathways, hinder OGs from transitioning into or contributing effectively to Horizon Europe projects.

2. *Perceived and actual benefits of OG participation*

Survey results showed that farmers value OG participation mainly for its practical outcomes, while broader benefits like strategic networking are seen as less relevant due to time constraints and immediate needs. Farmers need to see OG as a possibility to have visible results, not to be included only to fulfill MAA requirement. However, limited roles, tokenistic inclusion, and weaker personal connections – especially in virtual settings – undermine farmer engagement and the long-term impact of OG collaboration.

While OGs may have resources during their lifespan, they often lack the time, and once the project ends, they have time but no resources, making further engagement with HE difficult. Moreover, there is often no continuity plan to retain or build on the knowledge created during OGs, resulting in knowledge loss. Farmers are often seen as end-users rather than true partners and the leadership structures within OGs rarely allow farmers to take on central roles.

The extent to which they are meaningfully involved depends heavily on the attitude and inclusivity of the project coordinator.

3. Language as a structural barrier

Language barriers, particularly the dominance of English, continue to limit OG members (especially farmers) participation in Horizon Europe projects, excluding valuable local and tacit insights within EU-level innovation spaces. While translation tools exist, their limited integration highlights the need for more systematic support and accessible multilingual solutions.

4. Conclusion and recommendations

The session concluded that although interest in OG participation in Horizon Europe is high, various barriers hinder meaningful involvement. Addressing these challenges requires targeted communication, inclusive leadership, clearer participation pathways, language support, and practical tools to bridge local innovation with EU-level. Participants agreed that practical tools, such as mentorship schemes, onboarding tools and targeted networking platforms, are vital next steps to help OGs make the leap into Horizon Europe.

6.4.3 'Resources, skills, capacities of OG members to engage in Horizon MAA projects'

1. Challenges following the completion of EIP-AGRI OG projects

A major barrier to continued OG engagement after project completion is the loss of a central contact person, making communication and collaboration difficult. It is considered a "shame" that valuable knowledge and results are lost once the project is over, despite the resources involved, because contact persons are less active or available, and active entities may no longer be on the ground.

This challenge is compounded by the struggle OGs face in scaling up innovations and moving from pilot projects to wider adoption. Despite generating valuable innovations, OGs often lack the time, funding, and support needed to scale results and maintain momentum beyond the project's end. It is often challenging to integrate new technologies into practice once the project concludes as bringing innovative solutions to market requires more time and

financial resources. Integrating new technologies into practice requires significant time and financial resources, often exceeding the funding received during EIP OG activities. Rules regarding the use of European funds can also be restrictive, as they often do not support the promotion of new technologies in global markets outside the European Union.

There is a notable struggle with knowledge capitalization, as there is currently no central repository or stable network to ensure that innovations are implemented into real-life processes rather than being forgotten.

2. Administrative and linguistic barriers

Administrative burdens and bureaucratic hurdles remain a major deterrent for small farmers and companies attempting to participate in Horizon projects. OG members, especially farmers, face significant administrative, language and linguistic barriers when engaging with Horizon Europe, often lacking the resources and support to manage complex, English-based procedures in the project development phase. This administrative complexity and burden are particularly problematic for small agricultures or companies and can deter them from participating in OG or Horizon projects.

Language serves as a significant bottleneck, particularly for practitioners in countries where the local language is dominant; since all official Horizon Europe documentation and communication are in English. These actors often lack the specialized human resources and time required to navigate complex national and European regulations.

Beyond the literal language, there is also a disconnect between the technical language used in research and the practical language required by farmers. To overcome these issues, participants stressed the need for tailored regulations for OGs practical realities, with CAP Networks identified as key facilitators to understand HEU landscape.

3. Engagement of OGs in Horizon Europe projects

Regarding the engagement of OGs in larger projects, it was observed that contact persons are typically researchers from universities rather than the farmers themselves. These institutional partners are often chosen because they analyze results, write reports, and are better equipped to overcome language

barriers. Successful engagement in Horizon Europe requires strong institutional capacity, often necessitating a "good partner" or associative coordinator who can effectively help them see the vision of the project, explain and disseminate information. This dynamic means that while OGs bring invaluable local insights and practical knowledge, they are often represented indirectly, impacting the depth of their direct engagement. Participants warned against "token" inclusion where OGs are added simply to satisfy the multi-actor approach criteria without being central to the work.

To enhance Horizon Europe engagement, participants recommended sharing targeted HEU information with OG coordinators during or immediately after their active phase to improve continuity of the OG topic and involvement into next steps. There is also a lack of clear guidance and information on how OGs can specifically contribute, leading to confusion over whether "involvement" refers to a single representative or an entire consortium.

4. Potential benefits and strategic communication

The primary benefits for OGs participating in Horizon projects include access to innovation, funding for testing new products, and enhanced networking opportunities. OG members, farmers particularly value local, practical insights and peer-to-peer learning, often prioritizing the opinions of a "neighbor" over theoretical research.

Strategic communication is essential, with success stories and practical formats proving more effective than complex documentation. Peer-to-peer sharing, regional innovation markets and field visits were highlighted as an effective way to communicate experiences and promote learning within local communities. For communication to be successful, it must utilize simple, practical language and highlight success stories through media such as radio, television, and podcasts to deliver emotional and relatable messages.

A critical point is the financial compensation for farmers; if practitioners are expected to make a meaningful contribution to research, they should be compensated for their time as business owners rather than being expected to participate on a purely voluntary basis

Officials need to be more closely connected with the practitioners from OGs to improve the national legislation on EIP intervention. Highlighting tangible benefits helps demonstrate how OG participation in Horizon Europe can naturally extend innovation efforts.

6.4.4 'Role of OG members in Horizon project'

1. *Strengthening collaboration at national and EU Levels*

A significant challenge is the structural separation between the different support networks necessary for OG engagement. The EIP-AGRI support system (such as CAP Network and Innovation Support Services) and the Horizon Europe support structure (National Contact Points, NCPs) are often managed by different national ministries and possess distinct objectives, target groups, and ways of operating. This institutional separation creates a barrier to linking local practical innovation with EU-level research, particularly since personal contact and trust are crucial for consortium building.

Improved coordination between CAP networks, Innovation Support Services and National Contact Points is essential before engaging at the EU level. Strengthening institutional links between CAP networks, OGs, and Horizon Europe networks also at national level would address current structural separations and enhance collaboration.

2. *Improving guidance for OG involvement in Horizon Europe projects*

The operational nature of OGs – which focus on problem-solving and technical piloting (low to medium TRLs) and typically have a limited lifespan of about three years – clashes with the longer, more academically oriented research timelines (five to six years) of Horizon Europe projects. While the value of OGs lies in providing practical insights that address real-world challenges, integrating this practical focus into stringent scientific applications remains difficult without clear guidelines.

Tailored, technically grounded guidance will help Operational Groups contribute meaningfully to Horizon Europe projects. Practitioners require support to understand their potential roles within large research initiatives. This includes designating specific tasks or mandates for OG representatives

during the proposal phase to ensure they have a clear, functional role in the project. Simultaneously, researchers need better guidance on how to identify relevant OGs and understand the practical value these members bring to research proposals. Such support is particularly vital during the early "seed" phase of proposal development to ensure the multi-actor approach is properly established from the outset

Engagement should target both OG leaders and motivated members who value international collaboration, while clear, consistent evaluation criteria assess OG involvement in applied research.

3. Encouraging OG participation through incentives

Participants, particularly farmers and practitioners, stressed that they should be compensated for their time and contribution, as they are business owners who should not be expected to participate on a sustained voluntary basis. It was explicitly argued that if OGs are expected to have a meaningful involvement in Horizon Europe, they "must be compensated for [their] time as a business owner". For example, one farmer calculated that hiring someone to cover their work costs about €270 a day, underscoring the substantial investment farmers make when doing voluntary project work.

It was suggested introducing top-down funding mechanisms, such as seed funding, to stimulate early OG engagement in research projects. Projects that successfully involve OGs in applied research could be given extra weight during the assessment process.

Support for Scaling Up, with the recognition that OGs are typically practical and operational in nature, and may be hesitant to transition into research roles. Early support is essential to facilitate this shift. Guidance at the proposal building stage creates understanding of their role, what is expected from them from the very scratch, and what would be their future contribution within the project.

4. Clarifying terminology and enhancing communication

A critical challenge identified was the lack of clarity and consistency **in defining "OG involvement"**. This inconsistency causes confusion, as it is

unclear whether official requirements mandate the inclusion of the entire OG consortium or merely representatives.

Participants noted that involving an entire OG, especially large ones (e.g., 60 members), is practically impossible due to the immense legal and administrative burdens associated with getting universal agreement and managing such a large entity within a Horizon project structure. The use of generic terms like "OG involvement" in official documents, instead of "**OG member involvement**," can mistakenly signal reluctance and complexity, deterring participation. A clear definition of "OG involvement" is needed to specify whether it refers to the whole group, specific members, or individuals.

Harmonizing language between researchers and OGs will improve communication and ensure farmers' voices are inclusively represented. Communication must be improved by translating complex scientific objectives into practical language that practitioners can easily understand. Demystifying the perceived complexity of Horizon projects is most effective when done through peer-to-peer communication, where farmers with previous experience in Horizon projects share their success stories with others.

5. Leveraging existing tools and networks

Leveraging existing tools and networks involves increasing the visibility of the extensive OG database available on the EIP-AGRI website so that researchers can easily find relevant practitioners.

However, participants noted that databases are often insufficient on their own because successful collaboration depends on personal trust and "chemistry". Therefore, EIP-AGRI workshops and focus groups should be used as matchmaking forums where personal connections can be forged. These face-to-face interactions are often more reliable than digital tools for building the trust-based networks required for long-term project success.

It is necessary to utilize AKIS structures through building upon existing and former OGs, whose networks and knowledge remain valuable even after OG project completion.

6. Enabling flexible participation of OGs

One of the primary hurdles identified is the temporal difference between the two; OGs are typically funded for short-term tasks lasting two to three years, while Horizon projects often span five to six years. Because an OG legal entity may cease to exist before a Horizon project concludes (or starts), participants emphasized the need for a structure that allows for the continuity of knowledge even after the formal OG funding has ended.

Project evaluations should use clear criteria to give credit to appropriate and meaningful OG involvement in applied research sections of Horizon proposals. The involvement structure should favor individual participation of motivated members over the inclusion of the entire group to reduce administrative complexity, allowing OG representatives to contribute flexibly without requiring full partnership status when it is not necessary.

Flexibility is needed allowing OG representatives to contribute in specific roles within projects without requiring full partnership status. For those seeking less administrative intensive roles, options include acting as a subcontractor, an affiliated entity, or even an employee of a full partner, such as an advisory service or university. Other flexible participation models include serving on an advisory board, acting as a project "ambassador," or participating as a use case representative with financial compensation.

To make this participation effective, the group recommended that OGs nominate a specific representative to be given a clear mandate and defined tasks during the HEU project proposal phase. This ensures that practitioners have a functional, recognized role within the project rather than being limited to passive "stakeholder" consultations, which participants noted often fail to meet the requirements of a genuine multi-actor approach.

6.4.5 'Ensuring funding to fulfil the foreseen work'

1. *Information and guidance gaps*

Participants emphasized a significant information gap for OGs regarding Horizon Europe project participation, especially around funding, affecting all involvement phases from application to fund management. Most OGs have not received substantial advice from their national CAP networks or National Contact Points regarding Horizon participation. There is a perceived

disconnect between the heart of the EU, where needs are registered, and the national networks that must translate this into practical support.

Experts noted that a persistent myth exists regarding the administrative complexity of Horizon Europe, which is often misunderstood as being more difficult than other EU funds. They agreed that tailored guidance materials specifically for OGs, supported by national and regional structures and possibly facilitated by the PREMIERE project, are urgently needed to improve collaboration and financial navigation. Participants suggested the creation of a specific toolkit, communication products, or technical sheets that clearly describe the added value and practical benefits of participating in Horizon projects.

Inconsistent terminology between different policies was highlighted as a major barrier, necessitating a more unified language to facilitate cooperation.

2. Key financial considerations

A key concern was ensuring timely and appropriate funding for OG members participation, including clarity on beneficiary roles, funding mechanisms, distribution, and eligible costs aligned with HEU and CAP rules. The question is; how do we ensure that necessary funding of an OG involved in an HEU project, that reaches the right people to do the right work at the right time?

One innovative suggestion was to include a dedicated budget element or specific tasks within ongoing OG projects specifically to facilitate their engagement with Horizon Europe. Additionally, the group discussed the financial unattractiveness of subcontracting, noting that it does not generate the 25% overhead for partners and is frequently misinterpreted by evaluators as an intrinsic weakness in project design.

Participants also stressed the need for real-world examples and clear, jargon-free language to support learning and collaboration across projects. The main need is for guidance on how to assess which funding option is most appropriate in any given situation.

3. Legal and administrative uncertainty

Participants raised concerns about the legal and administrative status of OGs in HEU projects, particularly regarding representation, responsibilities, and beneficiary roles. Many OGs are not established as formal legal entities, which complicates their ability to sign non-disclosure agreements or act as official beneficiaries. The discussion highlighted the lack of a standard model for OG involvement, with varying levels of engagement depending on the project type and structure.

Various topical events are organised by the EIP-AGRI Support Unit / EU CAP Network to involve OG representatives in several events as individuals. While the lack of formalization is sometimes intentional to allow for personal capacity participation, it creates practical barriers during the proposal and implementation phases. Who exactly should be the legal representative(s) of the OG and therefore responsible for all administrative issues etc? What is the status/role of OG members that are not direct beneficiaries? Partners/beneficiaries from OGs should have meaningful engagement with the HEU project, including a meaningful project task. There can be a mismatch between the profile of OG members and the partners required in an HEU multi-actor project.

The sources indicate that excessive bureaucracy is viewed as a systemic barrier, exacerbated by a lack of guidance on how multi-actor projects should handle complex issues such as open data, GDPR, and intellectual property rights. This uncertainty often discourages OGs from taking on high-responsibility roles within a consortium.

4. Funding modalities and alignment

Participants discussed various funding options for OG involvement, emphasizing flexibility and cautioning that mechanisms like cascade funding may limit targeting due to eligibility constraints.

There is a critical need to align national CAP rules for OGs with Horizon Europe rules to allow lead partners to distribute funding using mechanisms that are already familiar to the practitioners. Experts emphasized that the choice of funding modality should depend on the maturity and experience of the participants, as a complex array of options can be intimidating to newcomers.

Finally, it was noted that Horizon participation should be framed as an opportunity for completed OGs to reform and continue their work, while ongoing OGs require better alignment to synchronize their strict work plans with the temporal development of Horizon projects

6.4.6 'Finding and aligning: how can OG members fit and be aligned in the HE call topics?'

A primary outcome of the discussion was the need to distinguish between different types of OG members, as advisors and researchers are typically already integrated into Horizon Europe, while farmers face the greatest difficulty in participating. For many farmers, the motivation to join an OG is driven by the need for immediate, practical solutions to current problems, whereas Horizon Europe projects operate on a much longer timeline.

A significant challenge identified by the group was the temporal misalignment between the two programs. While OGs are designed for rapid problem-solving and testing technical innovations within a year or two, Horizon Europe involves a lengthy process of partnership building, proposal writing, and a wait of at least one year before a project even begins. This requires farmers to act as long-term visionaries who look five to ten years into the future rather than focusing on the immediate needs of their farms. To better fit into HE calls, it was suggested that farmers could be integrated into projects at later stages to serve in piloting or testing roles that capitalize on their expertise as entrepreneurs and innovators.

The group also highlighted a gap in the existing support infrastructure for these members. While National Contact Points (NCPs) are experts in research and innovation programs like Horizon and LIFE, they often lack specific knowledge regarding farming possibilities. Conversely, AKIS nodes have the necessary expertise to support operational groups. A key recommendation from the discussion was that NCPs and AKIS nodes must work together to improve the transfer of information and help OG members navigate the complexities of Horizon Europe.

The barriers that cause OG members, particularly farmers, to remain passive participants in larger research projects include language barriers, specific knowledge gaps, and the high level of uncertainty regarding whether a

proposal will ultimately receive funding. To ensure OG members are not just passive recipients, the group emphasized that future efforts should focus on maximizing networking opportunities and encouraging members to actively shape the direction of research and innovation.

6.5 Annex 5: Mentimeter results – plenary session

In this annex you can find the results of the Mentimeter done the day of the Focus Group workshop, done during the plenary session.

Figure 23: Question used for the Mentimeter.

Figure 24: Question used for the Mentimeter.

Figure 25: Question used for the Mentimeter.

Figure 26: Question used for the Mentimeter.

Figure 1: Question used for the Mentimeter.

6.6 Annex 6: Plenary session slides

Here can be found the presentation used in the plenary session from the workshop.

**Role and importance of EIP-AGRI
Operational Group members in Horizon
Europe Multi-Actor projects**

Focus Group N° 3, 7 April 2025, 10:00-12:15 CET

**Susanne von Münchhausen (HNEE)
Hanna Tamsalu (METK)
Albert Escolà i Soles, Lluç Tost i Lopez (DARPA)
Jordi Pietx, Mark Redman (HCC)**

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